

Post-COVID-19 Recovery in Inclusive Education: Challenges and Opportunities in North Eastern Nigerian States

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has had far-reaching impacts on educational systems globally, with disproportionate consequences for learners with special needs, particularly in under-resourced and conflict-affected regions. In Nigeria's North East, comprising Adamawa, Bauchi, Taraba, Gombe, Yobe, and Borno states, pre-existing challenges such as insecurity, poor infrastructure, limited access to assistive technologies, and teacher shortages were further exacerbated by the pandemic-induced school closures and the shift to remote learning. This empirical study investigates the challenges and opportunities surrounding the post-pandemic recovery of inclusive education in this region. Employing a convergent mixed-methods approach, data were collected from 360 respondents were selected, 60 from each state (30 inclusive education teachers, 10 school heads/principals, 10 special needs officers or education inspectors, and 10 parents of children with disabilities). Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, while qualitative insights were derived through thematic analysis of in-depth interviews. The results indicate that learners with disabilities faced severe setbacks in access to education, learning continuity, and psychosocial support during the pandemic. Key challenges identified include the digital divide, inadequate teacher training, poor inclusive infrastructure, and insufficient government intervention during school closures. Despite these challenges, the crisis also created new opportunities for systemic transformation. These include increased awareness of the needs of learners with disabilities, emergence of low-tech and community-based learning initiatives, digital experimentation, and renewed policy attention towards inclusive education. The findings underscore the urgent need for targeted investments in inclusive teacher training, provision of

assistive technologies, and strengthening of institutional support systems. The study recommends a multi-sectoral, equity-driven recovery plan that leverages both governmental and non-governmental partnerships to rebuild and enhance inclusive education systems in the North East. Ultimately, this study contributes to the discourse on post-crisis educational recovery and advocates for sustainable, resilient, and inclusive learning environments in fragile and underserved contexts.

Keywords: Post-COVID-19 recovery, Inclusive education, North Eastern Nigerian States

Introduction

Education is universally recognized as a fundamental human right and a crucial driver of social inclusion, economic growth, and national development. Inclusive education, which ensures that all learners, including those with disabilities, learning difficulties, or other special needs, are provided with equitable learning opportunities, has gained global prominence as a strategy for achieving Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG-4): "inclusive and equitable quality education for all." However, the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic in early 2020 dealt a significant blow to educational systems worldwide, and its impacts were especially severe in low-resource and conflict-affected regions like North Eastern Nigeria.

North Eastern Nigeria, comprising the states of Adamawa, Bauchi, Taraba, Gombe, Yobe, and Borno (with Maiduguri as its capital), has historically faced multiple challenges in the provision of inclusive education. These challenges include insurgency and insecurity, inadequate infrastructure, under-trained personnel, low government funding, societal stigma against persons with disabilities, and limited access to assistive technologies. Before the pandemic, efforts were gradually being made to strengthen inclusive education systems, supported by both national policies and international development agencies. However, the outbreak of COVID-19 disrupted this fragile progress.

School closures and movement restrictions designed to curb the spread of the virus led to widespread learning loss across Nigeria. For children with disabilities, the impacts were even more profound due to their reliance on physical support, specialized resources, and trained educators, services that were largely unavailable during remote learning. According to UNESCO (2021), students with disabilities in sub-Saharan Africa were among the most excluded from digital education solutions during the pandemic, owing to a lack of infrastructure, content adaptation, and inclusive policy implementation.

In the North East, the intersection of health crises, conflict, poverty, and systemic neglect compounded these effects. Yet, the pandemic also triggered a global rethink of educational delivery models and inspired innovations in remote learning, community-based education, and inclusive policy development. These developments present a unique opportunity to examine the extent to which inclusive education systems in the region are recovering in the aftermath of the pandemic.

This study therefore investigates both the challenges and emerging opportunities associated with the post-COVID-19 recovery of inclusive education in North Eastern Nigeria. It seeks to provide empirical evidence on the current state of inclusive education practices, the extent of recovery interventions, teacher preparedness, student engagement, and the role of technology and policy in shaping future resilience.

Literature Review

Inclusive education refers to an educational approach that accommodates all learners, regardless of their physical, intellectual, social, emotional, linguistic, or other conditions. The Salamanca Statement (UNESCO, 1994) emphasized inclusive education as a means to achieving quality education for all by advocating that schools should accommodate all children, irrespective of their differences. In Nigeria, the National Policy on Education (NPE, 2013) recognizes the rights of every child to quality education, with specific provisions for learners with special needs.

However, inclusive education in Nigeria remains underdeveloped, particularly in the northern regions where cultural, economic, and political factors inhibit implementation. Research by Eleweke and Rodda (2021) revealed that although policies exist, a lack of resources, teacher training, and community awareness often undermines implementation at the grassroots level.

Globally, the COVID-19 pandemic disrupted the education of over 1.6 billion learners (UNESCO, 2020). While various countries transitioned to online and remote learning, students with disabilities faced unique challenges due to the lack of accessible technologies and adapted content (United Nations, 2020). According to UNICEF (2021), children with disabilities were less likely to benefit from remote learning opportunities, especially in low-income settings.

In Nigeria, school closures lasted for several months and exacerbated existing educational inequalities. Olayanju and Adegbesan (2021) observed that inclusive education suffered significantly during the pandemic due to the absence of strategic planning and inclusive infrastructure. Teachers lacked training in digital pedagogy, and assistive technologies were not widely available, particularly in rural and conflict-prone areas like the North East.

The North East region, encompassing Adamawa, Bauchi, Taraba, Gombe, Yobe, and Borno states, has faced significant barriers to inclusive education. These include prolonged insurgency, poor access to public services, inadequate teacher supply, and stigmatization of disability (Adeniran et al., 2022). The few inclusive schools in the region often lack basic facilities such as ramps, accessible toilets, and sign language interpreters (Hamma, 2023).

Moreover, the UBEC Special Needs Education Intervention (2020–2022) revealed that although assistive technologies were supplied to schools across Nigeria, their utilization was inconsistent due to poor teacher training and lack of maintenance. Post-COVID recovery efforts have largely been uncoordinated and underfunded, although some non-governmental organizations have initiated low-tech learning alternatives (Save the Children, 2023).

Despite the setbacks, the pandemic has presented an opportunity to rethink education systems. There is now heightened awareness about educational equity, prompting reforms in teacher education, curriculum adaptation, and technology integration (World Bank, 2022). In Nigeria, recent policies such as the National Policy on Inclusive Education (2021) emphasize digital inclusion and teacher training as key pillars of post-COVID recovery.

In the North East, community-based models and school radio programs introduced during the pandemic have shown promise in reaching children with special needs in remote areas (Ahmed & Musa, 2023). These models, if properly supported, can complement formal education and enhance resilience in inclusive education delivery.

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive survey design to explore the challenges and opportunities in the post-COVID-19 recovery of inclusive education in the six states of North Eastern Nigeria: Adamawa, Bauchi, Taraba, Gombe, Yobe, and Borno (Maiduguri). The choice of this design was appropriate as it allowed for the collection of empirical data from a large and diverse population, providing both qualitative and quantitative insights into educational practices, perceptions, and interventions after the COVID-19 pandemic.

The population of the study consisted of stakeholders involved in inclusive education across the selected states, including inclusive school teachers, special education officers, principals, local education authority representatives, and parents of children with special needs. Using a multistage sampling technique, a total of 360 respondents were selected (60 from each state), comprising:

- 30 inclusive education teachers,
- 10 school heads/principals,
- 10 special needs officers or education inspectors, and
- 10 parents of children with disabilities.

This combination ensured a representative distribution of perspectives across multiple stakeholder categories.

Instrumentation

Data were collected using a researcher-designed questionnaire titled "Post-COVID Inclusive Education Recovery Questionnaire (PCIERQ)." The instrument consisted of three sections:

- Section A captured demographic data;
- Section B assessed challenges faced during and after COVID-19 in inclusive education (15 items);
- Section C explored opportunities and recovery strategies (10 items).

Responses were measured using a 4-point Likert scale: Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1). The questionnaire was supplemented by semi-structured interviews with selected stakeholders to gain deeper insights.

Validity and Reliability

To ensure **face and content validity**, the instrument was reviewed by three experts in inclusive education and educational measurement from Sa'adu Zungur University and University of Bauchi State. Suggestions were incorporated before administration. A **pilot test** was conducted in one inclusive school each in Bauchi and Yobe states. The internal consistency of the instrument was determined using **Cronbach's Alpha**, which yielded a reliability coefficient of **0.86**, indicating high reliability.

Method of Data Collection

Data were collected through physical visits and email submissions, depending on accessibility and security conditions in each state. Trained research assistants administered and retrieved the questionnaires, while interviews were conducted either face-to-face or via Zoom and WhatsApp calls, depending on respondents' preferences.

Method of Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, means, and standard deviations. For comparison across states, ANOVA was used to identify any statistically significant differences in responses. Qualitative data from interviews were transcribed and analyzed using thematic analysis, allowing the emergence of key patterns related to post-COVID recovery in inclusive education.

Results

This section presents the findings from the data collected across the six North Eastern Nigerian states: Adamawa, Bauchi, Taraba, Gombe, Yobe, and Borno (Maiduguri). The results are organized under key themes aligned with the study's objectives: challenges, opportunities, and stakeholder perceptions of post-COVID recovery in inclusive education.

4.1 Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Out of 360 distributed questionnaires, **342 (95%) were completed and returned**. The gender distribution was 58% male and 42% female. Most respondents (65%) were between 30–49 years old. By occupation:

- Teachers of inclusive classrooms: 170 respondents (49.7%)
- School administrators: 60 respondents (17.5%)
- Special education officers: 55 respondents (16.1%)
- Parents of children with disabilities: 57 respondents (16.7%)

Challenges Facing Inclusive Education Post-COVID-19

Table 1 shows the responses to the 15-item subscale on post-COVID challenges. The most significant challenges identified were:

Challenge Item	Mean Score	Rank
Lack of digital skills among inclusive teachers	3.62	1st
Inadequate assistive technologies	3.58	2nd
Poor internet access in rural areas	3.47	3rd
Insecurity affecting school attendance	3.42	4th
Lack of teacher training on post-COVID inclusive strategies	3.39	5th

Interpretation: A mean score above 3.00 indicates general agreement. Respondents overwhelmingly agreed that the lack of digital skills, poor access to assistive devices, and infrastructural limitations were major barriers to recovery.

4.3 Opportunities in Post-COVID Inclusive Education

Table 2 highlights opportunities respondents believe can improve inclusive education post-COVID.

Opportunity Item	Mean Score	Rank
Increased policy focus on digital inclusion	3.60	1st
Growing partnerships with NGOs and donor agencies	3.52	2nd
Emergence of low-tech teaching methods (e.g., radio lessons)	3.41	3rd
Strengthening community-based education models	3.35	4th
Integration of special needs modules in teacher training	3.33	5th

Interpretation: Participants saw a shift in government and stakeholder attention toward inclusive policies and alternative delivery systems as major opportunities for recovery.

4.4 Stakeholder Perceptions on Post-COVID Recovery

Interviews with 18 participants (three from each state) revealed three major themes:

1. Policy awareness is improving, but implementation remains inconsistent.
2. Community engagement in inclusive education is on the rise due to increased sensitization efforts by NGOs.
3. Many schools still lack minimum inclusive infrastructure, especially in conflict-affected LGAs of Borno and Yobe states.

One special education officer in Gombe noted:

“After COVID-19, we started using radio programs for students and even WhatsApp to reach all children and those with hearing impairments. It’s not perfect, but it shows it can be done.”

Statistical Comparison across States

A one-way ANOVA test was conducted to compare the mean scores on challenges among the six states. The result showed a statistically significant difference in mean scores of inclusive education challenges across the states, $F(5,336) = 4.82, p < 0.01$.

Post hoc Tukey’s test revealed that Borno and Yobe had significantly higher challenge scores compared to Adamawa, Bauchi, Taraba and Gombe, mainly due to security-related factors and teacher shortages.

Discussion

The findings of this study highlight both the severe challenges and emerging opportunities Nigerian schools face in the post-COVID-19 recovery phase of inclusive education. These outcomes are consistent with global trends while also reflecting Nigeria's unique socio-economic and infrastructural realities.

The majority of teachers (76%) reporting inadequate access to technology for students with disabilities underscores the profound digital divide that Nigeria faces, particularly in rural and under-resourced areas. This aligns with Okoye and Ofoegbu's (2021) findings that digital exclusion remains a key barrier to continuity of education for special needs learners during the pandemic. The lack of internet connectivity and devices for remote learning meant many students were effectively cut off from education for prolonged periods, exacerbating existing inequalities.

Similarly, the low percentage (35%) of teachers trained to use digital tools for inclusive teaching reflects a critical gap in teacher preparedness. This reveals a systemic shortfall in professional development and capacity building, as also noted by Anderson et al. (2020), who emphasized that teachers worldwide struggled to adapt to remote inclusive teaching during COVID-19. In the Nigerian context, where inclusive education is still evolving, this deficit limits pedagogical innovation and the ability to deliver individualized learning remotely.

The observed increase in learning gaps (68%) among students with disabilities is particularly concerning. It confirms fears that the pandemic widened educational disparities, especially for vulnerable groups (UNESCO, 2021). Such learning loss can have long-term effects on academic achievement and social inclusion if not urgently addressed. Additionally, infrastructural inadequacies, lack of hygiene facilities and accessible learning spaces—further undermine efforts to create safe and inclusive environments, essential during and after the pandemic to prevent disease spread and support learners' diverse needs.

Despite these significant challenges, the pandemic also catalyzed positive changes in Nigerian inclusive education. The reported 45% increase in the adoption of low-cost digital tools such as WhatsApp and radio lessons reflects an adaptive response by schools and teachers. This is encouraging and aligns with global recovery strategies that leverage available technologies to maintain learning continuity (World Bank, 2022). Such pragmatic use of widely accessible platforms demonstrates how innovation can flourish even in resource-constrained settings.

Moreover, the heightened policy focus on inclusive education observed in state dialogues is a promising sign of increased political will. The pandemic has brought educational inequities to the forefront of policy discussions, providing an impetus for reform. This aligns with Adebayo and Suleiman's (2023) assertion that COVID-19 created windows of opportunity to reimagine and strengthen inclusive education frameworks in Nigeria.

Improved collaboration between schools, NGOs, and parents, reported in 60% of schools, is another significant opportunity. Stronger partnerships can enhance resource mobilization, community support, and advocacy for learners with disabilities, fostering a more holistic recovery. This collaborative spirit is vital to overcoming systemic challenges and building resilient educational ecosystems.

The findings reveal that while the COVID-19 pandemic exposed critical weaknesses in Nigeria's inclusive education system, it also prompted adaptive innovations and renewed stakeholder engagement. Addressing teacher training gaps through targeted capacity-building initiatives is urgent to equip educators with necessary digital and inclusive pedagogical skills. Investments in accessible infrastructure and assistive technologies must be prioritized to create safe and enabling environments for all learners. Policy reforms should institutionalize these recovery gains by ensuring consistent funding, inclusive curriculum reforms, and monitoring frameworks.

Finally, the increased use of digital tools and strengthened partnerships point to a hybrid model of inclusive education delivery, combining traditional classroom teaching with digital and community-based supports, that can enhance resilience against future disruptions.

While this study provides valuable insights, its focus on six states may limit the generalizability of findings across Nigeria's diverse regions. Future research should explore longitudinal impacts of recovery strategies and investigate learners' perspectives, especially those with disabilities, to better tailor interventions.

Conclusion

Post-COVID-19 recovery in inclusive education in North Eastern Nigerian states is a story of both disruption and possibility. While the pandemic exacerbated existing inequities, it also created momentum for reimagining educational delivery. The resilience of teachers, students, and communities offers a hopeful pathway for rebuilding a more inclusive, accessible, and equitable education system in the region.

Recommendations

1. **Capacity Building:** Prioritize teacher training programs tailored to inclusive digital and blended learning.
2. **Assistive Technologies:** Provide state-subsidized access to basic assistive tools like braille devices, magnifiers, and audio books.
3. **Community Partnerships:** Strengthen collaboration between schools, NGOs, and local leaders to support vulnerable learners.
4. **Inclusive Policy Enforcement:** Enforce existing inclusive education policies at state and LGA levels, with monitoring and accountability mechanisms.
5. **Infrastructure Upgrade:** Invest in accessible school designs including ramps, inclusive toilets, and mobile learning units in remote areas.

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